

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MULCHAN****FIRST NAME: NEIL****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

CRITICAL COMPONENTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) **INTRODUCTION**

The necessity to maintain appropriate international standards in all aspects of professional writing is of fundamental importance in research, journalism, manuscripts, and a plethora of other areas. Proper use of grammar, style, and mechanics may vary depending of geographical region, but these factors cannot be overshadowed by the overarching requirement to maintain the facets of content, integrity, purpose, and professionalism. This report seeks to address five key concepts inherent in all forms of academic writing.

2) **FIVE KEY CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING**

This report will examine several aspects of important criteria which should be considered necessary in the construction of academic essays. These criteria are important because techniques to develop because they promote writing skills that result in effective communication (Writing Skills | Skills You Need n.d.)

Five key components of academic essay writing will be introduced that, when implemented, will help to facilitate the achievement of high international standards of writing. I will consider the possible consequence that may stem from omitting each of these components, and suggest the benefit that each criterion may add to a literary body of work. The underlying theme is that the construction of a good essay should fulfil the fundamental criteria of answering a specific question. Within this context, the concepts addressed below attempt to demonstrate how this overall goal may be achieved.

a) Concept 1 – Purpose or Intent

The general purpose of most academic essays is typically to answer a question, solve a problem by offering a plausible, substantiated argument, or to add to an existing body of knowledge. “An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 1). This specific end goal should serve as the guiding path for all that is to follow, and should be clearly stated early in the writing. “A purpose statement is a declarative sentence which summarizes the specific topic and goals of a document” (PURPOSE STATEMENTS n.d.) This adds direction to the work for the author, and a focused interest from the perspective of the reader. Clearly stating the purpose or intent of the research creates a framework from which to progress, as well as provide boundaries to prevent digression.

b) Concept 2 – Organization and Planning

A structured approach outlining which aspects of the writing will be handled first, second, third, etc., may help alleviate anxiety and intimidation that often come with the seemingly monumental task of coherently bringing together numerous bits and pieces of data, facts, figures and ideas. In general, a brief list of what is to be undertaken in chronological order is a good starting point, and may include such things as materials used in the research and acquisition of data, details of discoveries made, supporting facts, and discussions of any possible sources of errors (Organizing Your Writing n.d.) A solid planning foundation provides a path that your essay can follow from beginning to end. These points may be summed up as follows: “Write all of this down in point form, and this will be your essay plan” (EUCLID 2019, 2).

c) Concept 3 – The Starting Point

This can sometimes be the most challenging aspect of academic writing – where to begin. A good place for this, as described in EUCLID 2019, is “Your starting point for an essay is your initial response to the topic or question. This response is based on what you already know” (1). Making use of what facts or ideas you are already comfortable with and believe to be sound, facilitates a skeletal backbone from which to expand your horizons with topics and ideas that you are less familiar with. Having this solid foundation of knowing what you already know, as redundant as that sounds, enables the generation of a comfort zone to which you can return to reformulate your ideas and reasoning when things seem to reach a dead end.

d) Concept 4 – Creative vs Critical Thinking

Two important facets of essay writing are creative and critical thinking. “Creative and critical thinking skills are considered essential for students” (Relationships-between-Critical-and-Creative-Thinking.Pdf n.d.) These do not simply apply to the expression of ideas on paper, but the cognitive approach to formulating ideas and the representation of the essay as a whole body of work. “Essay writing requires both creative and critical

thinking” (EUCLID 2019, 2). Creative thinking can help with the framework for the layout of presenting ideas in support of the purpose of the essay. Such ideas may include the physical layout of the different chapters, length of each chapter, font, style, color of graphs, size of charts, etc. All of these ideas are meant to present a well-formatted, coherent and chronologically represented body of work.

Critical thinking, on the other hand, is a more focused approach in the interpretation of results obtained from research, which in turn is to support the main question being answered. An effective and efficient way to express ideas such that it creates a vivid overall picture to the reader that strongly supports the case being made, is to periodically take a step back and think outside the box.

e) Concept 5 – Editing

In the latter stages of writing, as completion draws near, editing becomes the final, necessary hurdle. Over 100 years ago even Harvard University President Charles W. Elliot complained about what was tantamount to a lack of proper editing (Hull 1984). More often than not, each time the work is reviewed for errors, omissions, and grammar, changes will likely be necessary. As daunting a task as it may turn out to be, editing can only serve to strengthen the work by not only removing erroneous grammatical errors, but more subliminal aspects such as loopholes in your argument, or inefficiently juxtaposed supporting details.

A sound method for proper editing strategies is to partake in an editing workshop as described in one study “The literature review suggested improved instruction and evaluation through a writing workshop approach as a possible solution to the problem of poor revision skills” (Stemper 2002). As errors are discovered and the relevant changes made, care should be taken to fend off sometimes inevitable frustration, and as described in EUCLID 2019: “Don’t panic if/when you find faults in your essay – this is part of the process” (4).

3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, five key components important in academic essay writing have been discussed. The applicability and implementation of each idea was introduced with supporting research documentation, and the case made for the need to adhere to these criteria. The end goal is to produce a scholarly, professional, clear and compelling literary body of work that is held to high international academic standards. The report was successful to such an end.

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